

Building a Sustainable Joint between Rural and Urban Areas through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains

D2.3

Methodological recommendations and guidelines for LCA assessment

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Executive summary

This study is a part of BASAJAUN Project 'Building A Sustainable Joint Between Rural And Urban Areas Through Circular And Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains'. Project WP2 focuses on environmental aspects. It aims at providing recommendations and criteria to assess the performance of innovative materials and technologies and building systems developed in the project to improve material circularity in wooden construction.

The global objectives of WP2 are as follows:

- To select and propose indicators and impact assessment methods.
- To define a zero-waste strategy in wood-based construction.
- To support decisions for high level recycling of the wood-based construction products.
- To develop criteria and recommendations for the recovery.
- To provide the impact assessment results for the BASAJAUN products.
- To formulate recommendations for the standardization.

This deliverable D2.3 is provided in the context of the task T2.3: "Environmental impact assessment methods and approaches".

The present report draws up a non-exhaustive inventory of methods and standards helping to calculate environmental impacts from wooden materials. Certification systems attesting to materials, structures and buildings quality, especially on wood products, are also presented in the deliverable. A focus on Life Cycle Assessment principles is then realised. Finally, methodological guidelines and recommendations for the environmental assessment for BASAJAUN 'products' is proposed through examples.

Document history

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Glossary

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Full term</i>
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CEN TC	European Committee for Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation in French) Technical Committee
CI	Circularity Indicator
DGNB	German Sustainable Building Council (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen in German)
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
FU	Functional Unit (in LCA methodology)
HQE	High Quality Environmental standard (French certification)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
MCI	Material Circularity Indicator
MADASTER	The MAterial caDASTER
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
PCI	Product Circularity Index
PEF	Product Environmental Footprints
PEFCR	PEF Category Rules
RC-Tool	Recycling Tool (TUM)
RTS	The Building Information Foundation RTS sr. RTS Environmental classification system, Finland

1. Introduction

Concern about health and climate change problems lead consumers to pay growing attention to the ethical and environmental aspects of consumed products.

Materials manufacturers have many opportunities to respond to that need. Product environmental performance could be advertised with the manufacturer's self-declared claims, environmental labelling schemes or by providing life cycle assessment and reporting it as an environmental product declaration. It is important that environmental claims are accurate and substantiated, verified and not resulting to the misinterpretation.

According to the waste framework directive, material utilization by reuse and recycling should be the target for circularity rather than energy utilization. In the reuse case of products, it is obvious that considerable benefits could be achieved in raw material consumptions but environmental benefits depends whether the product in second use have the same quality performance as the product made from 'virgin' sources or not. Recently quality performance ratio is included to the calculation of life cycle assessment of reuse and recycling products.

In the recycling case, when transformation ends up to the different product than previously used, comparison should be made with the substituted product. In product utilization with material recovery and new transformation it is important, that loads from waste handling, processing and recycling do not exceed the benefits achieved.

This report will give an overview about environmental assessment methodologies, which are applicable for product manufacturers to claim their product environmental performance.

Finally, Life cycle assessment method is introduced, and calculation procedure is given for the BASAJAUN novel products assessments. The report is made mainly for the use of product manufacturers and LCA providers.

2. Environmental assessment methods and certification systems for materials, structures, and buildings with special focus on wood

2.1 Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)

2.1.1 General purpose of EPDs and methodology

An EPD is an independently verified and registered document that communicates quantified, verifiable, and accurate environmental information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. It also provides information on health related to emissions to indoor air, soil, and water during the use stage of the product. The EPD is produced based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) calculations. It is normally provided by the product manufacturer and must be verified by an independent expert. An EPD has a validity of 5 years.

The relevant standard for EPD is ISO 14025 (ISO 14025:2006), where they are referred to as "type III environmental declarations". The European standard EN 15804 "Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products" (EN 15804:2012 + A2:2019) provides calculation rules and guidelines in the construction sector. In addition, EN 15978 "Sustainability of construction works —Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method" (EN 15978:2011) governs the scope and the requirements for the application of EPD in building assessment.

The purpose of an EPD in the construction sector is to provide the basis for assessing buildings and other construction works, and identifying those, which cause less stress to the environment.

The core product category rules present in EN 15804 + A2 are to:

- define the parameters to be declared and the way in which they are collated and reported,
- describe which stages of a product's life cycle are considered in the EPD and which processes are to be included in the life cycle stages,
- define rules for the development of scenarios,
- define the rules for calculating the Life Cycle Inventory and the Life Cycle Impact Assessment underlying the EPD, including the specification of the data quality to be applied,
- define the rules for reporting predetermined, environmental and health information, that is not covered by LCA for a product, construction process and construction service where necessary,
- define the conditions under which construction products can be compared based on the information provided by EPD.

Concerning LCA methodology applied in EPD, some of the main rules recommended in the EN 15804 + A2 are related to the system boundaries, the allocation method, and the environmental indicators.

System boundaries

Indeed, EPD information are expressed in different modules, which allow easy organisation and expression of data packages throughout the life cycle of the product (Figure 1). The approach requires that the underlying data should be consistent, reproducible, and comparable.

Figure 1 Life cycle stages and modules for building assessment (EN 15804 + A2:2019)

Different types of EPD can be provided:

- **Cradle to gate:** Modules A1 to A3, C and D. These stages are the minimum to be declared for the default type of EPD,
- **Cradle to gate – specificity for construction products:** Modules A1 to A3. Modules C and D are not mandatory for construction products except for products containing biogenic carbon, where these modules must be included in the system boundaries,
- **Cradle to gate with options:** Modules A1 to A3, C and D plus additional modules (which can be A4 and/or A5 and/or module B),
- **Cradle to gate with options – specificity for construction products:** Modules A1 to A3 plus additional modules (which can be A4 and/or A5). Modules C and D are not mandatory for construction products except for products containing biogenic carbon, where these modules must be included in the system boundaries,
- **Cradle to grave and module D (modules A, B, C and D):** Module D takes into account the environmental benefits or loads resulting from reusable products or waste (Figure 2), recyclable materials and/or useful energy carriers leaving a product system e.g. as secondary materials or fuels.

Figure 2 Decision-tree for end-of-waste

Allocation methods

Allocation should be avoided as far as possible by dividing the unit process to be allocated into different sub-processes that can be allocated to the co-products and by collecting the input and output data related to these sub-processes.

When the unit process cannot be divided into sub-processes, co-products impacts must be allocated following these rules:

- when the difference in revenue from the co-products is low, allocation should be based on physical properties (e.g. mass or volume),
- In all other cases, allocation should be based on economic value.

In addition, material flows carrying specific inherent properties (e.g. energy or biogenic carbon content) have to be allocated reflecting the physical flows, irrespective of the allocation chosen for the process.

The choice of an allocation method is essential because it can have a significant impact depending on the product studied in LCA. Table 1 gives an example of the application of different allocation methods for the treatment of oak roundwood in French sawmills. For this example, we consider that the

roundwood process creates three different co-products: sawn timber, industrial wood without bark and bark. This process can also create waste (dust, etc.). Waste is not affected by the allocation rules because no environmental impact of the wood production is attributed to it.

Table 1 *Example of physical and economic allocation percentages applied to co-products from the processing of oak roundwood in French sawmills*

<i>Status</i>	<i>Product</i>	<i>Physical allocation (mass) (%)</i>	<i>Economic allocation (%)</i>
Coproduct	Sawn timber	53	96
Coproduct	Industrial wood	37	4
Coproduct	Bark	10	1
Waste	Dust	0	0

In the case of recycled materials used in another production process, these materials are considered as waste at the end of their “first” life. Thus, in terms of allocation, no environmental impact linked to their previous life is considered.

Environmental indicators

Some predetermined parameters are required and should be included in the EPD. They can be divided into three categories:

- Parameters describing environmental impacts: In the last amendment (15804 A2:2019), a distinction is made between core environmental impact categories (Table 2), which have to be evaluated, and additional impact categories, whose assessment is not mandatory if it is justified (0)
- Parameters describing resources use (Table 4),
- Other environmental information describing different waste categories and output flows (Table 5)

Table 2 *Parameters describing core environmental impacts*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Unit</i>
Global Warming Potential total (GWP-total)	kg CO2 eq. / FU
Global Warming Potential fossil fuels (GWP-fossil)	kg CO2 eq. / FU
Global Warming Potential biogenic (GWP-biogenic)	kg CO2 eq. / FU
Global Warming Potential land use and land use change (GWP-luluc)	kg CO2 eq. / FU
Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq. / FU
Acidification potential, Accumulated Exceedance (AP)	mol H+ eq. / FU
Eutrophication potential, fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (EP-freshwater)	kg PO4 eq. / FU
Eutrophication potential, fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (EP-marine)	kg N eq. / FU
Eutrophication potential, Accumulated Exceedance (EP-terrestrial)	mol N eq. / FU

Formation potential of tropospheric ozone (POCP)	kg NMVOC eq. / FU
Abiotic depletion potential (ADP minerals and metals) for non-fossil resources	kg Sb eq. / FU
Abiotic depletion potential (ADP-fossil) for fossil resources	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Water use	m ³ / FU

Table 3 *Parameters describing additional environmental impacts*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Unit</i>
Potential incidence of disease due to Particulate Matter emissions	Disease incidence / FU
Potential Human exposure efficiency relative to U235 (ionizing radiation)	kBq U235 eq. / FU
Potential Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (freshwater ecotoxicity)	CTUe / FU
Potential Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (cancer effects)	CTUh / FU
Potential Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (non-cancer effects)	CTUh / FU
Potential soil quality index (occupation and transformation land use impacts)	Dimensionless

Unlike the parameters describing environmental impacts, resource use parameters are flow indicators that quantify impact sources without evaluating the effect of these sources on the environment.

Table 4 *Parameters describing resource use*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Unit</i>
Use of renewable primary energy excluding renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Use of renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Total use of renewable primary energy resources	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Use of non renewable primary energy excluding non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Use of non-renewable primary energy resources used as raw materials	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Total use of non-renewable primary energy resources	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Use of secondary material	kg / FU
Use of renewable secondary fuels	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Use of non-renewable secondary fuels	MJ (net calorific value) / FU
Net use of fresh water	m ³ / FU

Table 5 *Parameters describing waste categories and output flows*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Unit</i>
Hazardous waste disposed	kg / FU
Non-hazardous waste disposed	kg / FU
Radioactive waste disposed	kg / FU
Components for re-use	kg / FU
Materials for recycling	kg / FU
Materials for energy recovery	kg / FU
Exported energy	MJ per energy carrier / FU

2.2 Product environmental footprints (PEF)

2.2.1 General purpose of Product Environmental Footprints

Since 2011, the European Commission has developed the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method as a common way of measuring environmental performance (JRC, 2012). In order to answer the main discussions raised by the scientific community and to improve the methodology, the JRC published a set of suggestions in 2019 (Zampori and Pant, 2019).

PEF method is based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to quantify the environmental impacts of a good or a service throughout its life cycle. Its overarching purpose is to enable to reduce the environmental impacts of goods and services taking into account supply chain activities (from extraction of raw materials, through material production and use to the final waste management process). This purpose is achieved through the provision of detailed requirements for modelling the environmental impacts of the flows of material/energy, the emissions and waste streams associated with a product throughout its life cycle.

PEF method is applicable in the construction sector and a respective PEF Category Rules (PEFCR) was produced, whereas the EN 15804 exists and seem to have the same goal.

Recently, Durão et al. (2020) realised a comparative analysis of these two methodologies and their respective requirements and PCR. This study showed that there were initially important methodological divergences between PEF and EN 15804 methods, mainly on the system boundaries, the allocation rules, the environmental indicators assessed with LCA and the characterisation methods associated. However, in the last revision of the EN 15804 (EN 15804:2012 + A2:2019), a great effort was operated to harmonize PCR from this standard with PEFCR. Nevertheless, EN 15804 cannot be yet replaced with PEF method. Indeed, comparability is clearly stated as the main objective of the PEF method and very strict PEFCR are provided to reach this goal. However, it remains a global method and it does not consider some specificities of the construction sector, which make EN 15804 still essential.

2.2.2 PEF in BASAJAUN project: example of the existing PEFCR for thermal insulation materials

In 2013, the PEF pilot phase was launched to test the method and develop PEFCRs for 14 selected product categories (first wave of tests), whose thermal insulation materials. On this work basis, a report on these PEFCRs for thermal insulation was produced and updated in 2019 (CD2E, 2019). However, these

PEFCRs are provided for specific thermal insulation products only (Table 6).

Table 6 PEFCRs scope for thermal insulations materials

Application	Product	Reference
Pitched roof with massive timber rafters	Loose fill cellulose	ETA –EN 15101*
Non-accessible flat roofs with concrete structure	Un-faced cellular glass board	EN 13167: 2015
	Un-faced EPS grey board	EN 13163: 2015
	Faced PU board	EN 13165: 2015

* Pending citation in European official journal

The associated functional unit is defined as: “Thermal insulation of X m² of a building element, with an insulation thickness that gives a thermal transmittance U_c of the element as defined in the vertical rules, with a design life span of 50 years”. The value of X shall be defined in the vertical rules, which are specific rules for each product belonging to the scope.

Each PEF study carried out in compliance with this PEFCR shall consider the system boundaries presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 System boundaries for thermal insulation products.

The EF impact assessment shall include all categories listed in Table 7 below.

Table 7 List of the impact categories to be used to calculate the PEF profile

Impact category	Indicator	Unit	Recommended default LCIA method
Climate change			
Climate change-biogenic	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO _{2eq}	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC (based on IPCC 2013)
Climate change –land use and land transformation			
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 _{eq}	Steady-state ODPs 1999 as in WMO assessment
Human toxicity, cancer effects*	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh	USEtox model (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects*			
Particulate matter	Impact on human health	disease incidence	UNEP recommended model (Fantke et al 2016)
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ²³⁵	kBq U ^{235eq}	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995 (Frischknecht et al, 2000)
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOCeq	LOTOS-EUROS model (Van Zelm et al, 2008) as implemented in ReCiPe
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H+eq	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol Neq	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg Peq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009b) as implemented in ReCiPe
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg Neq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009b) as implemented in ReCiPe
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	CTUe	USEtox model, (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)
Land use		- Dimensionless	
		(pt)	- Soil quality index based on LANCA (EC-JRC)
		- kg biotic production	- LANCA (Beck et al. 2010)
		- kg soil	- LANCA (Beck et al. 2010)
		- m ³ water	- LANCA (Beck et al. 2010)
		- m ³ groundwater	- LANCA (Beck et al. 2010)
Water use**	User deprivation potential (deprivation-	m ³ worldeq	Available WATER REMaining (AWARE) Boulay et al., 2016

	weighted water consumption)		
Resource use, minerals and metals***	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sbeq	CML 2002 (Guinée et al., 2002) and van Oers et al. 2002.
Resource use, fossils	Abiotic resource depletion –fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ	CML 2002 (Guinée et al., 2002) and van Oers et al. 2002

*Long-term emissions (occurring beyond 100 years) shall be excluded from the impact assessment. If included by the applicant in the LCI modelling, the sub-compartment 'unspecified (long-term)' shall be used. Toxicity emissions to this sub-compartment are not included and have a characterisation factor 0.

** The results for water use might be overestimated and shall therefore be interpreted with caution. Some of the EF datasets tendered during the pilot phase and used in this PEFCR/OEFSR include inconsistencies in the regionalization and elementary flow implementations. This problem has nothing to do with the impact assessment method or the implementability of EF methods, but occurred during the technical development of some of the datasets. The PEFCR/OEFSR remains valid and usable. The affected EF datasets will be corrected by mid-2019. At that time, it will be possible to review this PEFCR/OEFSR accordingly, if seen necessary

***The ADP crustal content/ultimate reserves is considered as an intermediate recommendation in terms of life cycle impact assessment method. The results of this impact category shall be interpreted with caution, because the results of ADP after normalization may be overestimated. The EU Commission in cooperation with industry intends to develop a new method moving from depletion to dissipation model to better quantify the potential for conservation of resources.

As an example, the following figure (Figure 4) represents LCA outputs, using the PEF method, resulting from the comparison between the production processes of 1 kg of glass wool, 1 kg of rock wool and 1 kg of wood wool. These processes come from the Ecoinvent database, which is the most consistent life cycle inventory database used for LCA.

Figure 4 Example of LCA results using the PEF method: comparison of the production processes of glass wool, rock wool and wood wool.

2.3 Green product/building assessment and certification systems

2.3.1 Environmental labelling of products

Environmental labels operating as informative, voluntary instruments for the market. Environmental labels and declarations can help consumers to identify those products or services proven 'environmentally preferable'. ISO defines three type of product environmental labels: Type I, Type II and Type III.

Type I label is on behalf of a third party. It contains several classification criteria's and in case product fulfils those, it can be informed that product complying with this environmental label. Principles and procedure for applying Type I label is described and guided in international standard (ISO 14024, 2018). It including the selection of product categories, product environmental criteria and product function characteristics, but also for assessing and demonstrating compliance.

Type II label is environmental claim based on the company's own declaration. The standard defines the terms and sets general requirements for the label (e.g. must not be misleading, etc.) (ISO 14021, 2016). The international standard describes selected terms commonly used in environmental claims and gives qualifications for their use, it also describes a general evaluation and verification methodology for self-declared environmental claims and specific evaluation and verification methods for the selected claims in this International Standard. For example, verifiable terms such as 'made from x% recycled material' are permitted.

Type III environmental statement (declaration) contains quantified environmental information of the product using pre-set parameter categories. The calculation is based on ISO 14040 series of standards. Principles and procedures for applying Type III based information is described in ISO standard (ISO 14025, 2006). This declaration is primarily intended for use in business-to-business communication, but their use in business-to-consumer communication under certain conditions is not precluded. Environmental product declarations are Type III statement.

2.3.2 Carbon handprint

'Carbon Handprint - communicating the good we do' project was held in 2016-2018. Carbon handprint methodology was created together with VTT (as a coordinator), Lappeenranta University of Technology and industry partners.

The aim of Carbon handprint was to create a transparent, robust, and scientific based tool to assess and communicate carbon handprint, which can be used in marketing and branding.

'Carbon handprint' calculates beneficial environmental impacts that manufacturer can achieve by providing products with reduced footprints. Carbon handprint of a product is based on evaluating the difference between the current used product and baseline footprint solution.

Quantification of the carbon handprint is based on a carbon footprint calculation consisting of a life cycle assessment (LCA) that is limited to GHG emissions. Expertise in LCA and a thorough knowledge of the ISO 14067 standard on the carbon footprint of products is therefore a necessity.

Figure 5 Carbon handprint guide (<https://www.handprint.fi/carbon-handprint/>)

2.3.3 Building life cycle assessment, Level(s)

Consistent life cycle based method, Level(s), is developed by the European Commission for sustainability reporting of the building and construction sector. Level(s) assessment based on the life cycle assessment standard for the buildings (EN 15978:2011). The idea was to propose a baseline (common language) for the assessment and benchmarking. The assessor has possibility to choose assessment level: simplified level, assessment for the comparison of the buildings with the same performance and assessment for the optimization.

Method has six essential criteria's: Life cycle based carbon footprint, resource efficient use of materials, water consumption, healthy spaces and indoor air quality, resilience to the climate change and life cycle costs. All the criteria contain sub-criteria's for the assessment.

First Level(s) assessment version was tested in EU member states and feedback from this test was delivered to European Commission for the purpose of development of Level(s). In Finland, it was pointed out that the most acute needs for development include improving the clarity and accessibility of the guidance document, restructuring of the assessment levels and reconsideration of the system boundaries.

2.3.4 Green building certification and rating systems

Building certification systems has been developed for assessing environmental quality of buildings. Great number of building certification systems exists; and most known from them are BREEAM (UK), DGNB (Germany), HQE (France), Miljöbyggnad (Sweden), RTS (Finland), LEED (US), CASBEE (Japan).

The focus of certification in those systems is different:

- Even so, that the system is launched in particular country, some of them including also localized versions and are widely used in many countries, while other are used only in one country, because has been designed only for the use of specific climate and country needs.
- Assessment level depends also on the country based building regulations. Main known regulation includes country-based level for energy efficiency, but also other regulated issues like comfort, air quality, water conservation etc. may exist.

- Certification systems are many categories in which some are available in almost all systems while other uses only some of them or include category, which other does not handle.
- Some of the systems meant for the assessment of all building types while others have assessment versions according to the building types.

Comparison of those systems is somewhat complicated as the rating proportions are also differ between the systems. However, publication Simply Green tries to give a quick review to environmental and energy certification systems for sustainable buildings (Swegon air academy, 2012). Even so, that it is written already in 2012, in general, it gives a good picture about the systems assessed.

Main assessment categories are energy, indoor environment, water, materials, site, construction phase, transport, economy, innovation and then other. For the circular economy point of view, most interesting categories are those, related to the handle and credits given for the waste, material and innovations but also for final rating. Selection of parameters in category Materials, Waste and Innovations are given in Table 8 and rating in Figure 6.

Waste category related to the waste management, innovations related to the use of new technologies and materials related to the material origin, environmental aspects and recycling.

Table 8 Selection of parameters in Category materials, waste, and innovation (in building certification systems).

	BREEAM	DGNB	HQE	Miljö- byggnad	RTS	LEED	CASBEE	Geen Star	IGBC
MATERIALS									
Recycling	x	x	x			x	x	x	x
Environ- mental aspects	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Origin	x		x			x	x		x
WASTE									
Waste management	x	x	x			x		x	x
INNOVATION									
Innovation, new technologies	x				x	x		x	x

BREEAM - Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method, UK (www.breeam.org)

DGNB - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen, Germany (www.dgnb.de)

HQE -France (www.assohqe.org)

Miljöbyggnad - Environmental Building, Sweden (www.sgbc.se)

RTS - Environmental classification system, Finland (<https://cer.rts.fi/en/rts-environmental-classification/tool/>)

LEED - Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design, US (www.usgbc.org)

CASBEE - Comprehensive Assessment System for Built Environment Efficiency, Japan (<http://www.ibec.or.jp/CASBEE/english/>)

GreenStar - Environmental Certification system, Australia (www.gbca.org.au)

IGBC - India's GreenBuilding Council certification system, India (www.igbc.in)

Figure 6 Certification systems and ratings for the categories of 'material', 'waste' and 'innovation' (from the total).

Certification systems are introduced in WBDG web site (<https://www.wbdg.org/resources/green-building-standards-and-certification-systems>) but also in their specific sites given above.

2.4 Circularity metering by Material Flow Analysis

2.4.1 Assessment levels for the circular use of resources

According to the New Circular Economy Action Plan of the European Union, circular products should be produced in an environmental-friendly way and with an efficient use of resources. To use resources more effectively, Circular Economy aims to increase the use of secondary raw materials in new products. Thus, to reach circularity, the consideration of waste generation and linked material streams is an important aspect to be considered. These aspects also have to be faced to make the construction sector become circular. (European Commission 2015)

Circularity can be assessed at different levels. In literature, the definitions of these levels vary. According to Lindner et al. (2017) with reference to Zhu et al. (2011), the assessment at macro level covers the national or regional context. At meso level, cities or industrial parks or the supply chain are considered. The assessment of companies or products takes place at micro level. In contrast to the macro and the meso level, there is a lack of assessment methods at micro level. (Niero et al. 2018)

2.4.2 Material Flow Analysis

To assess material streams in terms of circularity, Material Flow Analysis (MFA) can be applied, measuring material streams and stocks that enter and leave a considered system. It has to be taken into account, that outputs from one system might become the input for another system. With the application of Material Flow Analysis, only the amount of materials can be evaluated. Thus, Material Flow Analysis connected with other evaluation methods enables a comprehensive assessment of circularity including for example a quality analysis. (Elia et al. 2017; Guo et al. 2019; Rincón et al. 2013; Virtanen et al. 2019)

For metering circularity, in addition to the Material Flow Analysis, often *circularity indicators* are applied, which should ensure a precise and practical means to evaluate a product's performance in the background of circularity. (Saidani et al. 2017; Virtanen et al. 2019)

In 2015, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation developed the *Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)* to measure the circularity at company or product level. For the calculation of the indicator for non-renewable materials and technical cycles, a bill of materials for the considered products has to be generated. The bill includes aspects like the amount of secondary material used for the production of the product and the use period of a product. Further, the use at end-of-life and the performance of the recycling processes have to be taken into consideration for every material. These necessary inputs to calculate the MCI are shown in Figure 7 (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2015).

Figure 7 Inputs to calculate the Material circularity Indicator (MCI) for products (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2015)

2.4.3 Circularity metering methods in construction

For the circularity assessment in construction, different concepts exist or are currently developed to measure circularity at building, component, or material level. In the following, methods for the circularity assessment of constructions are presented.

LEVEL(s)

As already mentioned in chapter 2.3.3, in the European setting, *Level(s)*, which is still being evaluated and will presumably be ready for the market this autumn, should form a first harmonized framework to assess the sustainability performance of a building. The framework is exemplarily used across Europe to see if the application is convenient. To measure the sustainability performance of a building, the tool sets indicators that must be assessed. These indicators are related to energy and resource consumption, the generation of waste, to water and to indoor air quality. The indicator “Resource efficient and circular material life cycles” aims for circularity by the improvement of design and construction and by prolonging the lifetime of materials and the influence on the environment. The evaluation can be conducted at three different levels dependent on the purpose of using the results. For level one (*common assessment level*) and two (*comparative assessment level*), the results of the assessment must be indicated with the reference unit of m² useful floor space/yr. The results of the

third level, which is the *optimized performance level*, the reference unit of m² useful floor space/yr. or different units can be applied (Dodd et al. 2017; European Commission 2020).

Buildings as Material Banks - BAMB

Within the EU funded project *Building as Material Banks* under the acronym *BAMB*, a platform is being developed, which provides the generation of material passports of buildings. Additionally, a *Decision Making Model* should enable the evaluation of buildings in consideration of the resource efficiency, respecting a demolition free disassembly. Developed out of this model, the *Circular Building Assessment prototype CBA*, which is still being verified in pilot projects, will connect BIM or CAD models with data from *BAMB* and other sources. Thus, additional data about the resource efficiency of a building can be provided. To design reversible buildings, a protocol should promote and advance easy disassembly for buildings. (BAMB 2020a, 2020b, 2020c)

The analyzation of the reversibility of buildings includes spatial, structural and technical dimensions. Structural dimensions refer to materials and connection that enable damage free disassembly. Spatial aspects to evaluate reversibility are for example the designing principles like the structure and the size of the building and the available capacities (e.g. space) to change easily the function of buildings. The technical reversibility assessment at building, system or component level contains the aspects functional, technical and physical decomposition. Reversible constructions are characterized by functional independences and exchangeability. In addition, component design aspects, which are linked to reusable constructions and resource efficiency, are taken into account. With the generation of a spider diagram, the reversibility of a construction can be graphically shown. In addition, a relation pattern diagram demonstrates the relations between functional groups (horizontally) including aspects like for example technical disassembly (vertical, within one functional group) with respect to the connections, the way of assembly and the materials and the material function's life cycle. This analyzation helps to improve the reversibility of constructions. An example of a spider and a relation pattern diagram to assess reversibility of an extension module have been generated during a case study of the *BAMB* project for the evaluation of the *Green Transformable Building* laboratory GTB (see Figure 8) (Durmisevic 2018; Goens et al. 2017).

DISASSEMBLY ANALYSIS EXTENSION MODULE

structure and material levels	
14x elements/ 5x components/ 1x material	0.4
relational pattern	
7x horizontal relations/ 25x vertical relations	0.4
base element specification	
system level - intermediary between systems	1.0
component level - intermediary between systems	1.0
no-base element 3x	0.1
standardization of product edge	
9x pre-made geometry, 10x half standardized geometry, 1x no standardized geometry (geometry made on construction site) = $((9 \times 1) + (10 \times 0.5) + (1 \times 0.1)) / 20 =$	0.71
assembly direction	
Gravity attractor - lateral	0.9
functional dependence	
Modular zoning	1.0
type of connection	
26 x direct connection with additional fixing device	0.6
9x direct connection btwn two pre-made component	0.4
4x indirect connection with third chemical material	0.2
$((26 \times 0.6) + (9 \times 0.4) + (4 \times 0.2)) / 39 =$	0.51

Relation Pattern Diagram

Figure 8 Spider and Relation Pattern Diagram for an extension module according to Goens et al. (2017)

Spider Diagram

DISASSEMBLY ANALYSIS EXTENSION MODULE

structure and material levels

14x elements/ 5x components/ 1x material 0,4

relational pattern

7x horizontal relations/ 25x vertical relations 0,4

base element specification

system level - intermediary between systems 1,0

component level - intermediary between systems 1,0

no-base element 3x 0,1

standardization of product edge

9x pre-made geometry, 10x half standardized geometry,

1x no standardized geometry (geometry made on construction site) = $\frac{\{9 \times 1\} + \{10 \times 0,5\} + \{1 \times 0,1\}}{20} = 0,71$

assembly direction

Gravity attractor - lateral 0,9

functional dependence

Modular zoning 1,0

type of connection

26 x direct connection with additional fixing device 0,6

9x direct connection btwn two pre-made component 0,4

4x indirect connection with third chemical material 0,2

$\frac{\{26 \times 0,6\} + \{9 \times 0,4\} + \{4 \times 0,2\}}{39} = 0,51$

Relation Pattern Diagram

Figure 9 Spider and Relation Pattern Diagram for an extension module according to Goens et al. (2017).

Madaster

On the *Madaster* platform material passports of buildings can be created with the information provided by architects, engineers or building owners. The unit of the material amounts have to be provided with reference to the functional unit m, m², or m³. In addition, with information about the materials concerning the construction, use and end-of-life stages, a *Circularity Indicator* (CI) at building level can be determined. This indicator, based on the *Material Circularity Indicators* (MCI) of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, shows circularity indicator of a building. If a building holds a *Circularity Indicator* of 0%, it is not circular at all. Whereas a *Circularity Indicator* of 100% indicates that a building is totally circular. The circularity assessment of a building contains the consideration of the percentage of secondary materials (construction), the functional lifetime of a product relative to the average

functional lifetime (use) and the share of material, which can be recovered at end-of-life. Together, the three indicators form the *CI* score. This score is finally modified with two factors depending on the data integrity. Heisel und Rau-Oberhuber (2020) assessed the module *UMAR* as part of the *NEST* building. Until now, this is the only scientific assessment of a building with the *Madaster* tool. The figure below (Figure 10) shows the results of the circularity evaluation of the module. In the figure, the *Madaster CI Score* shows the calculated *Circularity Indicators* without taking into account the factors for the consideration of the data integrity. In the *CI Building Score*, these factors are considered (Heisel und Rau-Oberhuber 2020; Broonsoort und van Oppen 2020).

Figure 10 *Madaster circularity evaluation results for UMAR module (Heisel et al. 2020).*

Model for the Recyclability of Building Components – Recycling Tool

For the assessment of construction components and the assessment of different component alternatives, the *Recycling Tool* by TUM, which has already been described in D5.1, provides transparent results of component disassembly and output material streams, which can be shown graphically and in precise numbers. The comparison of the results helps to improve iteratively the component's performance concerning its environmental impact and its recyclability in comparative studies. The calculation is based on the standards DIN EN 15804, DIN EN 15978, DIN EN ISO 14040 and DIN EN ISO 14044 as well as the German standard DIN 8580 defining joining methods and already clearly determined material (re-) cycle scenarios. Separate results for the environmental impact of the analysed component and the resource use (component-based material flow at end of life) are given. Both results refer to a component specific functional unit that makes upscaling possible (Ebert et al. 2020).

The following generic examples for different ceiling (wood-beamed, concrete) and wall components (concrete, solid wood) give an overview of the results that can be generated with the tool. As the calculated environmental impacts are based on EPDs, the results are the typical LCA results. For the Material Flow Analysis at end of life or more specific the waste material flows, masses of the materials per functional unit are taken into account and the results are presented relatively to the total mass of the component per functional unit as well as in absolute numbers per functional unit. Results can alternatively be calculated in reference to the component's volume. A consistent calculation and comparison of different components or different component alternatives helps to improve existing or new components in terms of circularity. For the comparison based on the same functional unit, the components have to be characterized by an equal U-value or, if structural components are assessed, the same load bearing capacity sets the basis for the comparison. For an easier analysis and

interpretation, the results are visualized and color-coded dependent on the waste hierarchy (Figure 11)

1	MRU	Material for Re-Use
2	MSM	Material for Secondary Material Use
3	MMR	Material for Material recovery
4	MMRf	Material for for final/one-time Material Recovery
5	MERf	Material for final/one-time Energy Recovery
6	MWD	Material for Waste and Disposal

Figure 11 Color-coding of the waste hierarchy within the Recycling-tool according to Ebert et al. (2020).

For construction products, it is necessary not only to assess every single material, because the connections between the materials significantly influence a material's recyclability at end of life. Thus, the recycling tool helps the user to consider the connections between the different layers within a construction component.

At first, the results for the two different wall components are being presented below. Exemplarily, for the environmental impact only the results for the GWP, as well as the PENRE, PERE are shown in Table 9.

Table 9 Results of the recyclability assessment of a solid wood wall and a concrete wall according to Ebert et al. (2020)

Construcion	Solid wood wall	Concrete wall
Component layers		
Total mass [kg/m²]	85,8 (100%)	540,1 (100%)
Environmental impact per m² component area (Modules A1-C4)		
GWP [kg-CO₂-Äq./m²]	24,3	84,6
PERE+PENRE [MJ/m²]	695	817
Recyclability per m² component area		
MRU Material for reuse [kg/m ²]	8,7 (10%)	0,0
MSM Material for secondary material use [kg/m ²]	0,0	21,0 (3%)
MMR Material for Material Recovery [kg/m ²]	8,8 (10%)	393,0 (74%)
MMRf Material for final/one-time Material Recovery [kg/m ²]	0,0	89,0 (16%)
MERf Material for final/one-time Energy Recovery [kg/m ²]	67,4 (80%)	0,0
MWD Material for Waste and Disposal [kg/m ²]	0,0	37,9 (7%)

For the exterior wall components, the results are exemplarily visualized with a tree map, showing the mass [kg] per m² wall area (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Recyclability of components and materials – mass per m² wall area according to Ebert et al. (2020).

The circularity charts below show the percentile distribution of the masses in the exterior wall components according to the waste hierarchy (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Recyclability of components and materials – percentage

In addition, for different ceiling constructions the results of the environmental impact and the recyclability assessment are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Results of the recyclability assessment of a solid concrete ceiling and a wood-beamed ceiling.

Construcion	Solid concrete ceiling	Wood-beamed ceiling
Component layers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sisal carpet, d= 6mm Concrete C20/25, d=300mm Steel fibre, amount 1,4% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Linoleum, d=2,5mm Screed calcium sulphate, d=35mm Mineral wool, d=20mm Grit, d=60mm Coating spruce, d=40mm KVH, (b/h=140/260mm; e=600mm)
Total mass over life cycle [kg/m²]	745,04 (100%)	379,55 (100%)
Environmental impact per m² component area (Modules A/B/C)		
GWP [kg-CO₂-Äq./m²]	81,3	57,3
PERE+PENRE [MJ/m²]	927,76	1505,1
Recyclability per m² component area		
MRU Material for reuse [kg/m²]	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
MSM Material for secondary material use [kg/m²]	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
MMR Material for Material Recovery [kg/m²]	577,39 (78%)	270,26 (71%)
MMRf Material for final/one-time Material Recovery [kg/m²]	119,62 (16%)	56,36 (15%)
MERf Material for final/one-time Energy Recovery [kg/m²]	1,96 (0%)	31,53 (8%)
MWD Material for Waste and Disposal [kg/m²]	46,07 (6%)	21,40 (6%)

The results showing the recyclability of the components in tree maps are, like the results for the exterior walls once presented, relatively to the total mass of the component (Figure 14).

Figure 14 Recyclability of components and materials – mass per m² ceiling area

Also, the mass ratio in consideration of the recyclability of the different materials within the component is visualized in a circularity chart in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Recyclability or circularity capability of components and materials according to waste hierarchy level – in percentage

2.4.4 Critical Review on Existing Methods

The consideration of the different methods to assess circularity in construction shows, that nowadays very different ways of metering circularity exist.

According to Cottafava und Ritzen (2020), so far, the processes to assess circularity with methods provided by platforms like Madaster are not precise enough and thus, have to be improved. Yet, a perfectly consistent and precise method to assess circularity in construction does not exist. In addition, the often-applied circularity indicators still need to be improved, because they are mainly developed by consultancy companies. Thus, currently their development is not sufficiently based on research. Moreover, they generally focus on the mass of materials or the sustainability of resources or mix both up. Until now, all the existing indicators to assess circularity show weaknesses at some point of the assessment. Also, the current indicators barely focus on the broader micro level of the building to assess circularity of products. For a consistent and valid circularity metering, which evaluates a product's quality, the evaluation should concentrate on component and products level and other aspects such as the assessment of the product's environmental quality should not be contained (Lindner et al. 2017; Saidani et al. 2017; Cottafava und Ritzen 2020).

Further, Lindner et al. (2017) state that the results of the measurement or a circularity indicator should be *reliable* and *transparent*, as is required for LCA. Meaning that the results should not be easily influenceable and can be cross-checked by others. *Unambiguous methodological principles* should prevent the influence of personal experiences, favours or concerns on the assessment. To ensure *generality* in the circularity assessment, it is important to eliminate influence from any industrial or technical institutions and to make the application of the assessment possible for many different products. Moreover, aggregation principles should be applied to ensure only one conclusive indicator to measure circularity (Lindner et al. 2017).

Based on these observed weaknesses of circularity assessment methods, Table 11 shows relevant aspects to transparently measure circularity. Based on the aspects the described assessment methods contained in *LEVEL(s)*, *BAMB*, *Madaster* and the *Recycling Tool* are considered. The first aspect evaluates if the method is based on *Material Flow Analysis*. As already mentioned, the reason for this is, that, combined with other assessment methods, a transparent means is given to evaluate material

streams, their quantities and qualities. As the reference to a specific functional unit is important for the comparison of results, this aspect is also accounted. Lindner et al. (2017) emphasize that the evaluation of circularity and the evaluation of other quality aspects, such as the assessment of environmental impacts, should not be mixed, thus this aspect can also be found in the table. Further, circularity assessment in construction can be related to either buildings, components or materials. Under which scope the considered methods are applied is also listed in Table 11.

Table 11 Aspects of transparent circularity assessment in construction for different circularity metering methods

	<i>Material Flow Analysis</i>	<i>Functional unit</i>	<i>Separation of circularity and other quality aspects</i>	<i>Building/Component/ Material level</i>
LEVEL(s)	yes	m ² useful floor space/yr. or other units for 3 rd level	no	Building Level
BAMB	no info	no info	no info	Mixture
Madaster	yes	m ³	yes	Building Level
Recycling-Tool	yes	m ² (on standard product)	yes	Component level

Table 11 shows, that the considered methods to assess circularity are, besides the *BAMB* method, based on *Material Flow Analysis*. The results of *LEVEL(s)*, *Madaster* and the *Recycling Tool* all refer to functional units. The separation of circularity and other quality aspects is only fulfilled by *Madaster* and the *Recycling Tool*. Contrarily, *LEVEL(s)* combines different aspects including the environmental impacts within one indicator. The presented methods are being applied at different construction levels. Further, the *Madaster* platform for example analyses entire buildings, whereas the *Recycling Tool* can be used for the analyzation of components as well. The assessment within *BAMB* does, in the author’s point of view, not clearly focus on one specific level.

To conclude, presented circularity metering methods are still not fully transparent, subjective and show quantitative results. For the correct assessment of circularity in construction, objective, measurable and transparent methods, which enable a quantitative evaluation, are required. Thus, the combination of different methods should be considered. The *Material Flow Analysis* and *Circularity Indicators* seem to be appropriate for this purpose, if scientific aspects like transparency, reliability and generality are respected. For example, the *Recycling Tool*, which is based on *Material Flow Analysis*, could be one small part of many to meter circularity in construction by measuring the recyclability of building components. Hence, the combination with other methods could lead to a robust metric for circularity assessment in construction. Manufacturers who want to improve their products have to keep circularity assessments very detailed for their products and manufacturing processes. This is the only way to detect weaknesses or gaps in a circular economy and use resources more efficiently. Finally, it is recommended to perform a circularity assessment together with an LCA to exploit important synergies in material cycles, secondary energy use or substitution and improve the overall assessment results and products.

3. Life cycle assessment methodology

Life cycle assessment (LCA) analyses the environmental aspects and potential impacts across the product life cycle from cradle to grave, including raw material acquisition, production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling, and final disposal.

LCA is a technique that has been developed to gain a better understanding of the potential environmental impacts of products. LCA can help in:

- identifying opportunities to improve the environmental performance of products at different life cycle stages,
- selecting relevant indicators of environmental performance,
- informing decision-makers in industry, government, or non-government organizations,
- marketing products.

The LCA methodology is described in standards ISO 14040 “Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework” and ISO 14044 “Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines”. These standards present the requirements for carrying out an LCA, such as its different realisation stages. These phases are presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 The four phases of Life Cycle Assessment (ISO 14040:2006)

3.1 Goal and scope definition

The goal definition phase determines the goal of a study.

The scope includes information about the studied product system, such as its functions, the functional unit, the system boundaries, the allocation rules, the assumptions realised, etc.

The functional unit is the reference value that forms the basis for comparisons between all inputs and outputs. LCA is structured around the functional unit that defines what is being studied.

System boundaries define all the unit processes, which will be included in the studied system and considered in the LCA. These boundaries depend on the subject and the intended use of the study. Consequently, results of different LCA studies cannot be compared with each other without careful consideration of their functional units, system boundaries and assumptions related to calculations.

3.2 Inventory analysis

Life cycle inventory (LCI) is the second phase of LCA. It aims at compiling information about the inputs (consumed by the studied system) and the outputs (produced from the system) throughout the product life cycle.

For each life cycle stage, inventoried data are:

- raw material, energy, and other physical inputs,
- products, co-products and waste produced,
- Emissions to air, water and soil generated during the production processes.

During this inventory phase, collected data must be expressed in relation to the defined functional unit.

3.3 Impact assessment

In the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, potential environmental impacts are evaluated using the LCI results. LCIA involves associating inventory data with potential environmental impacts.

Several stages can be distinguished in LCIA phase:

- selection of the characterisation methodology and the studied impact categories,
- assignment of LCI results (called classification stage),
- calculation of the potential environmental impact for each studied impact category (called characterization stage).

In addition, normalization can be done. Normalized impact category results are dimensionless and enable the comparison of different impact category results against each other.

3.4 Interpretation

Interpretation correspond to the last phase of LCA. It aims at interpreting the results of the inventory analysis and impact assessment phases in relation to the objectives of the study.

It usually is completed by complementary analysis such as sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, which help getting information on the robustness of the results. This is essential to use LCA as a tool for decision-making. These analyses assess the influence on the results of variations in inventoried process data, model choices or other variables.

In the sensitivity analysis, these changes are deliberately introduced to determine the robustness of the results with regard to these variations.

The uncertainty analysis uses empirical data on the uncertainty ranges of specific data to calculate the total error range of the results.

3.5 European standard EN 15804

The European standard EN 15804 provides core product category rules for Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) for construction products. Some of these rules concern LCA by defining guidelines for LCI calculation and LCIA.

In BASAJAUN project, in order to be consistent with EPD system, this European standard is used as a general methodological frame for LCA. This means, recommendations in this standard are applied for BASAJAUN LCA, and namely:

- The system boundaries: BASAJAUN LCA cover all life cycle stages (LCA from “cradle to grave”) from A1 to C4 with the addition of the module D (Figure 1).
- The allocation rules: Allocation shall be based on physical properties (e.g. mass or volume) when the difference in revenue from the co-products is low, in all other cases, allocation shall be based on economic values.
- The environmental indicators: Core environmental impact indicators, parameters describing resource use, information describing waste categories, output flows and biogenic carbon content will be included in each module declared.

3.6 Eco-design approach

During the last decades, the eco-design approach has become an important way towards more sustainable manufacturing processes. The concept of eco-design is defined as an approach allowing to “produce products responsibly to be safe and sustainable, and ensure that, whenever possible, the end of products’ life cycle is the birth of something new” (Singh and Sarkar, 2019). The eco-design approach aims at optimizing the inputs and outputs of the production process; reducing fossil energy, water, and material consumption; minimizing the environmental impact by reducing the emissions and waste production and enhancing the product efficiency.

Indeed, recycling processes have to be taken into account in the eco-design approach. Closed-loop and open-loop recycling are distinguished. In closed-loop recycling, the properties of the recycled material are not too different from those of the virgin material. Thus, the recycled material can substitute to the virgin material and be used in the same way as before, so the product is recycled back into itself. In open-loop recycling, the properties of the recycled material and those of the virgin material are too different. Thus, the recycled material is only usable for other product applications where it can substitute to other materials.

Eco-design approach is based on Life Cycle Assessment principles. Thus, it considers the entire life cycle of a product from cradle to grave. A significant number of eco-design methodologies and tools exist and have been developed by researchers to help industries to apply this concept (Table 12).

Table 12 *Example of some of the most used eco-design methods and tools (adapted from Singh and Sarkar, 2019)*

<i>Method/Tool</i>	<i>Description</i>
Sustainability Assessment Framework and Tool (SAFT)	Provides cross-disciplinary evaluation to identify concerns from multiple criteria.
Screening life cycle modelling (SLCM)	Evaluates the effects of promising product concepts by creating life cycle scenarios.
DfE matrix	Provides scores to a product to track the improvements in its life cycle impact.
MET-matrix (Material, Energy and Toxicity)	Helps to identify the environmental load of the materials, energy and toxicity of products.
ABC analysis	Provides ranking to the impacts caused by a product.
LiDS wheel	Lists out the strategies to reduce the impacts of a product life cycle.
Eco-it	Identifies the parts of the products that cause the major impacts.
MIPS	Indicates the resource utilization by a product for providing per unit of a service.
The eco-design indicator tool	Builds the life cycle profile of a product for the measurement of its impact.
Trade-off modelling method Carnahan-Thurston	Evaluates the designer's estimates for different design alternatives of a product.

Eco-design approach is realised in the early stages of the product development. Indeed, the cost of changing the design and the composition of the product keeps on increasing as we move further during its development. Thus, it is essential to take all key decisions concerning the design and the composition of the product before its development.

Eco-design approach is described in the standard ISO/TR 14062:2002 "Environmental management — integrating environmental aspects into product design and development", which describes concepts and current practices relating to the integration of environmental aspects into product design and development. In addition, the European standard ISO 14006:2020 "Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating eco-design" gives guidelines for assisting organizations in establishing, implementing and continually improving their management of eco-design as part of an environmental management system.

In addition to environmental benefits, the eco-design approach also represents different opportunities to companies from economic and social perspectives (Table 13).

Table 13 *Internal and external drivers for eco-design in companies, regarding environmental, economic and social aspect (Sanyé-Mengual et al. 2014)*

	<i>Internal drivers</i>	<i>External drivers</i>
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease of resources consumption - Decrease of environmental impact - Increase of efficiency - Enhance environmental management systems - Continuous improvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of environmental communication - Compliance with environmental legislation - Contribution to global sustainability
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable cost savings - Fixed cost reduction - Introduction into new markets - Development of new products - Improved product quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market differentiation - Green purchasing - Supply for new green market demands - Enhance of supply chain information
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved company image. - Enhance of innovation and entrepreneurship. - Increased staff motivation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental awareness - Environmental responsibility

In addition of these benefits, economic applicability of the innovation resulting from eco-design has to be taken into account, just like the technical feasibility of this innovation. Thus, it is essential since the better innovation from an environmental point of view can be completely unusable if it leads to uncompensated additional costs or technically unrealistic solutions.

These eco-design difficulties can be illustrated by some examples based on Garnica's experience with its attempts to apply eco-design approach on its products. In the case of SIP (Structural Insulated Panel), the use of bio based insulation core in the panel change the production system: it makes it more manual, requires greater amount of material inputs, increases the need of structural requirements in the final product and leads to a loss of industrialization in the process. These are big drawbacks for any production line.

Another example of difficulties encountered by Garnica relates to Wood Plastic Composite (WPC) laminate wood board. Indeed, the addition of WPC laminate onto the top of a wood board allows the use of lower aesthetic quality plywood in the product. Adhesion of this WPC sheet on the plywood is an issue. After some laboratory testing, it seems that the more economical solution leading to the better adhesion of WPC sheet is performed with higher amount of wood. However, the final application of WPC products, in furniture in general, is less demanding than requirements in the construction sector (concerning fire performance or mechanical resistance for examples), so in this case, board thickness should be lower and final appearance more critical. Here, the outcome from the eco-design approach leads to a proposition that opposes to technical requests of the product.

The eco-design approach can be quite difficult to apply for some industrials. Continuing with the Garnica's case, by now, practically all the materials used in its products still come from virgin sources rather than using recycled materials. Although they generate by-product (as sawn milled and shredded wood) that can be recyclable for other industrials processes or energy production. In addition, it could be used in the new development (WPC) for plywood/SIP product although they did not try it yet with Garnica's own wood waste. Within BASAJAUN project some tests could be performed to assess this possibility.

4. Guidelines for the environmental assessment and circular economy for BASAJAUN 'products'

4.1 BASAJAUN, new products and systems

BASAJAUN project will develop new eco-innovative products and construction systems through a holistic transformation of the wood sector. Those innovative wood-based construction materials are thermal insulation, composites, varnishes, and SIPs, but also construction systems like facades, floors, walls, roof and fixings systems. BASAJAUN materials and construction systems will be then piloted in demo buildings, in France and Finland, and will be reported separately in D5.7 Components for demo buildings (not available during this writing).

Table 14 shows the BASAJAUN-products and existing products, which are widely used, but BASAJAUN products can thus compensate (substitute) them.

Life cycle assessments for BASAJAUN products and environmental impact assessment will be provided in BASAJAUN WP2 deliverable D2.4, 'LCA Assessment of the BASAJAUN materials and components' (not available during this writing). Those materials and products will be assessed using method and indicators, defined, and suggested in this report, for current used products, existing EPDs will be used.

Table 14 *BASAJAUN products and potential products for BASAJAUN product substitution*

<i>BASAJAUN products</i>	<i>Main product for BASAJAUN substitution</i>	<i>Other potentials for BASAJAUN substitution</i>	<i>Use case</i>
Insulation	Polymer insulation (XPS)	- Mineral wools (Stone and Glass) - Currently wooden insulation	- SIP panel - Other insulation
Thermoplastic composites	-Wooden boards, protection layers for SIP - Hot pressing sheets	- Decking, cladding, profiles, stairs - Sandwich structure for transport and construction (+wooden foamed insulation)	Exterior or interior use
Coating (UV protector)	Fossil based resins	- Facades - Outdoor furniture, - Etc.	Wooden based envelope (façade, windows, etc.)
Coating (insecticide)	Insecticide treatments of the substrate (Solvent based)		INSECTICIDE for wooden materials (SIPs, GLULAM, LVL, PLYWOOD, MDF, PB) for indoor applications
Coatings	-Fire retardant treatments of the substrate -Active fire protection: sprinklers	- Fire proofing of other wooden materials: CLT, LVL, WPC - Other substrates: Plastics, metals.	Fire protection of wooden materials (SIPs, GLULAM, LVL, PLYWOOD, MDF, PB) for indoor applications
Multilayer system	Wooden boards, protection layers for HPL GARNICA's PLYWOOD (Pine)- Hot pressing Sheets Wood plastic composite sheets to improve low grade plywood aesthetic surface and fire performance behaviour (WKI product)	- Roofing, - Furniture, - Cladding, - Sandwich structure for transport and Construction (+Wooden foamed insulation)	Protected layer for GARNICA's SIP, boards

Insulation system: one of the main goals within the building sector is the substitution of XPS foam core by a more sustainable material (bio-based foam) maintaining similar or better technical effectiveness at a reasonable cost.

Thermoplastic composites: focused on polymer-based composites is referred to the development of sustainable composites, development of Wood Plastic Composite (WPC) or Natural Fibre Composites (NFC). The innovation here comes that source raw material come from residues (plastic/wood). Some of the main goals to fulfil are fire retardancy (indoor products) and durability (outdoor products). Multilayer systems are also interesting option since some additional performances could be achieved taking into account secondary or recycled materials. Aesthetic and superior quality material is the objective to drive material to roofing, cladding, frames and profiles or furniture applications. Plastic Composite (WPC) laminate pressed on the top of Garnica´s SIP/Plywood is one of product development example.

Coatings: Different functionalities are being developed to protect wood-based surfaces against some of the main problems that are constantly facing wood-based buildings. Indeed, diverse solutions will be developed in terms of outdoor durability, fire retardancy and biological resistance for wood-based products to be used in the demo buildings.

Table 15 *BASAJAUN products/systems and material source (potential use of waste and recycling materials).*

<i>BASAJAUN products</i>	<i>Material type</i>	<i>Material source</i>
Insulation	Wood fibres/ wood flour	- 'Virgin' wood - Product waste (used insulation after end of life), - Wooden construction and demolition waste - Wooden side stream waste
Thermoplastic composites	- Wood fibres /wood flour - Polyethene and Polypropylene	- 'Virgin wood' - Wooden construction and demolition waste - Recycled PE and PP (packaging waste)
SIP1	- wood fibres /wood dust - veneer	- According to the 'Insulation' - Veneer (from virgin source)
SIP2	-Wood fibres /wood flour - Wood plastic composite (WPC)	- According to the 'Insulation' - WPC1 virgin wood, wood from process residues, milling dust Bio plastics (for example PLA) recycled bio plastics - WPC2 virgin wood wood from process residues, milling dust, fossil based plastic (for example HDPE) fossil based recycled plastic

Methodological aspects for the Life Cycle Assessment of the products, structures, and buildings, where waste, process residues and recycled materials have been used, are shown in next chapters for BASAJAUN product calculations.

4.2 BASAJAUN product development. SIP/Plywood with top WPC layer

Circularity and sustainable management of materials and elements are the base of products developed in BASAJAUN project. As an example, development of one specific product that consists of SIP/Plywood with top WPC layer is presented. The use of secondary materials to enhance properties is one of the main goals to improve currently marketed products. Therefore, adding and external layer of WPC onto wood board (SIP/Plywood) expects an improvement in aesthetics, fire retardancy or outdoor performance. In addition, development of this WPC top layer is expected to be based on recycled polymers (or bio based sourced) and waste wood out of industrial scrap. In this context,

Garnica produces several tons of wood flour and derivatives during their internal milling, cutting and productive operations. This raw material ends up mixed altogether (different species, different particle size) in silos and apart from waste to energy solutions there are not so far, other better circular solutions for this waste stream. In fact, it can be said the use of recycled materials in wood-polymer composites (WPC) is currently restricted to the polymer source (Mauruschat, 2016).

At present recycled wood resources from processing and construction residues are hardly used for the manufacturing of WPC. Presence of elements such as preservatives, adhesives or glues have prevented using of recycled wood in new WPC products. Besides, there is a lack of international uniform criteria for the classification of wood waste groups. In the other hand, some companies use recycled polymers due to cost issues and because high-quality recycled polymers are available which fulfil the required specifications. However, at present, recycled wood resources from processing and construction residues are hardly used for the manufacturing of composites. Such resources represent an unexploited, valuable raw material source for WPC and provide a significant contribution to the circular economy.

Some of Garnica´s initial requirements and specifications:

- Garnica manufactures plywood as a wood-based product for diverse applications: like SIP, formworks, furniture, non-structural uses, others.
- WPC layer, produced by recycled material can be used as a top layer for non-aesthetic plywood or wood boards, mainly poplar but also could be pine or eucalyptus. This composite would substitute High Pressure Laminate (HPL)
- Although not characterized yet, some contaminants may appear in wood flour waste, such as glues (Phenolic, MUF) minor amounts of Flame Retardants or biocides. Only the case of wood treated with preservatives is considered critical case since some of these products have been classified as hazardous for humans and need to be retired from the rest of potentially recyclable wood fraction. The rest could be a potential raw material for new products. Indeed, as an example, only 33% of the wood waste produced in Germany were used as raw material to produce particleboards and the rest ended up burnt in incineration plants to deliver electricity (Mauruschat, 2016). Therefore, it is clear that it is a huge potential for up to now discarded wood fractions. In fact, according to some studies, presence of some residues such as adhesives, glues or resins could enhance hydrophobicity of WPC composites improving outdoor performance and durability of products (Teuber et al. 2015).
- Plywood sheet dimensions 2500mm x 1270mm x (1-1.5) mm and 3170mm x 1570mm x (1-1.5) mm. Tolerance +/- 0.1 mm.
- Surface of wood product need to be smooth and uniform to stick WPC layer properly onto wood surface. Good adhesion is needed.
- UV and fire resistance (ideally B-s1, d0) are mandatory for developed WPC system and for the whole product if finally is placed as a part of the building. If material does not reach specifications other applications (for instance, furniture) are possible, being final requirements less demanding compared to construction.

Product development procedure:

- The base product will be SIP/Plywood produced by Garnica. Some modifications are suggested to improve sustainability.
- In current Garnica´s SIP product substitution of XPS core foam by a bio-based foam is one option to boost sustainability.
- WPC layer will be place on the top of plywood to enhance aesthetical appearance keeping same functionality. This WPC layer is based on recycled/bio-based polymer matrix plus wood waste raw material out of production activity. Additives to enhance outdoor behaviour and fire retardancy are included in the formulation through extrusion (compounding)
- Screening of polymer matrix (HDPE, PLA, PMMA, PA10) and wood flour sources and systems to be studied. Adhesion, fire performance and mechanical tests to be carried out to select more promising system.
- WPC sheets are pressed onto the plywood by a press moulding equipment, a) through hot pressing at 80-95°C using finely ground compound as a bonding agent or b) using glues and adhesives to stick both WPC and Wood surfaces (cold pressing).
- Keep industrial automatization and avoid handmade operations at maximum.
- Sustainability, outdoor durability, fire-performance or mechanical behaviour to be studied.
- Final price will depend on the achievable properties. The more demanding properties the more valuable and costly material. The goal is to reach high performance applications and if this is no possible, get one-step down to lower requirement products. Regarding environmental issues, a balance in the amount of used secondary raw material and functionality (upscaling) is one of company's interests when developing new products.

Figure 17 Process for the manufacturing of poplar plywood (Garnica)

Figure 18 General product development procedure and possible applications.

4.3 Calculation of Module A, raw material source

Raw material to produce BASAJAUN new product would be obtained from virgin material (primary source) $M_{VM\ in}$ and from material recycled from previous system $M_{MR\ in}$ (M represents material parameter). Wooden based recovered materials would be used also for energy production as a secondary fuel $M_{ER\ in}$:

- Secondary fuel is the material, which reached the end-of-waste state before incineration in a previous system and enters the product system as secondary fuel) and the amount equals the output flow of “materials for energy recovery [kg]” of a previous system.

Parameter E is used in calculations for representing specific emissions and resources consumed per unit of analysis (it is calculated for each impact category, for example global warming impact and other).

- $E_{VM\ in}$ is those impacts arising from acquisition and pre-processing of primary material in the production of the product.
- $E_{MR\ after\ EoW\ in}$ is those arising from material recovery processes (recycling) of the previous system after the end-of waste state.
- $E_{ER\ after\ EoW\ in}$ is the impact from arising from combustion of secondary fuel entering from a previous system (having reached the end-of-waste state).

Life cycle Module A (emissions and resources per unit of output) should take into account emissions and resources from energy consumption, coming from primary energy sources e_{PE} but also from recycled materials and secondary fuels.

Impact calculation $e_{module\ A}$ for the BASAJAUN products and production stage are shown below for four material recovery case:

Case 1. BASAJAUN raw materials obtained 100% from virgin sources and energy obtained 100% from primary sources:

$$e_{module\ A} = M_{VM\ in} * E_{VM\ in} + e_{PE} \quad (Eq.1)$$

Case 2. BASAJAUN raw materials obtained 100% from recycled materials and 100% of energy obtained from primary sources:

$$e_{\text{module A}} = M_{\text{MR in}} * E_{\text{MR after EoW in}} + e_{\text{PE}} \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Case 3. BASAJAUN raw materials obtained 100% from recycled materials, recovered material used also as a fuel (secondary source) and energy obtained from primary sources:

$$e_{\text{module A}} = M_{\text{MR in}} * E_{\text{MR after EoW in}} + M_{\text{ER in}} * E_{\text{ER after EoW in}} + e_{\text{PE}} \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

Case 4. Part of BASAJAUN raw materials obtained from virgin sources, other part from recycled materials, recovered material used as a fuel (secondary source) and energy obtained from primary sources:

$$e_{\text{module A}} = M_{\text{VM in}} * E_{\text{VM in}} + M_{\text{MR in}} * E_{\text{MR after EoW in}} + M_{\text{ER in}} * E_{\text{ER after EoW in}} + e_{\text{PE}} \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

4.4 Calculation of End of life for different scenarios, Module C

Alternatives for the material utilization of BASAJAUN products will be studied in BASAJAUN WP2, Task 4. This will be reported in BASAJAUN deliverable D2.5 (End of Life - recyclability and reusability assessment of the BASAJAUN products). During writing, this report about recyclability was not completed and because of that, End of life calculation for the BASAJAUN products based on appointed scenarios rather than real cases. According to the waste handling, four End of life calculation case is shown below:

Case 1. Wastes from BASAJAUN products will be recovered for material use (before their end of waste status). Impacts from recovery process should be reported in life cycle stage C3:

$$e_{\text{module C}} = M_{\text{MRout}} * E_{\text{MR before EoW out}} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

Case2. Waste from BASAJAUN product will be recovered for the energy production, i.e. waste will become a secondary fuel (the material reaches end of waste before incineration), process occurring before the end of waste stage. Calculated impacts should be reported in life cycle stage C3.

$$e_{\text{module C}} = M_{\text{ERout}} * E_{\text{ER before EoW out}} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Case 3. Wastes from BASAJAUN product will be used for energy recovery from waste (incineration). In case, when energy recovered with efficiency greater than 60 %, calculated impacts should be reported in life cycle stage C3 and with efficiency lower than 60 %, impact should be reported in life cycle stage C4.

$$e_{\text{module C}} = M_{\text{INC out}} * E_{\text{INC}} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

Case 4. After the end of life BASAJAUN products will be landfilled. Impacts from landfilling should be reported in life cycle stage C4.

$$e_{\text{module C}} = M_{\text{LF}} * E_{\text{LF}} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

4.5 Module D calculation, different material recovery routes

Information module D is beyond the system boundary, as it considers potential impacts, which might happen after the end of material/structure first life.

Module D ($e_{\text{module D}}$) expresses environmental loads ($e_{\text{module DL}}$) and benefits ($e_{\text{module DB}}$) beyond the buildings life cycle resulting from different recovery routes such as recycling of materials, reusing of products and recovery of energy leaving the product system.

$$e_{\text{module D}} = e_{\text{module DL}} - e_{\text{module DB}} \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

The loads are always calculated as impacts related to the recovery process and the benefits are calculated as the avoided impacts related to avoided production of primary (virgin) materials or energy. Total module D is a sum of all impacts: from possible recovery routes of secondary materials ($e_{\text{module D1}}$), secondary fuels ($e_{\text{module D2}}$), energy resulting from waste incineration ($e_{\text{module D3}}$) and energy as result of landfilling ($e_{\text{module D4}}$).

$$e_{\text{module D}} = e_{\text{module D1}} + e_{\text{module D2}} + e_{\text{module D3}} + e_{\text{module D4}} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

In case of material recovery, quality ratio between outgoing recovered material ($Q_{R,\text{out}}$) and substituted material (Q_{Sub}) should be assessed. In the case of BASAJAUN products it will material recycling and the ratio expressed as $Q_{R,\text{out}} / Q_{\text{Sub}}$. Assessment stage D1 ($e_{\text{module D1}}$) (for the use of secondary material) should be calculated as follows:

$$e_{\text{module D1}} = M_{\text{MR out}} - M_{\text{MR in}} * (E_{\text{MR after EoW out}} - E_{\text{VSub out}} * Q_{R,\text{out}} / Q_{\text{Sub}}) \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

4.6 Example of calculation of modules A, C and D on climate change

For this example, an Oriented Strand Board (OSB) is considered. Table 16 presents the main characteristics of the studied OSB.

Table 16 *Characteristics of the panel considered in the example.*

Panel thickness	16 mm
Panel density	670 kg/m ³
Panel moisture	4.4%
Type of glue	PMDI

The results below were obtained with the EN 15804 + A2 characterisation method.

Table 17 presents the different cases studied and the results for module A on the climate change indicator.

Table 17 *Parameters and results of module A*

Cases	Situation	Parameters	$e_{\text{module A}}$ (kg CO2e/m ²)
Case 1	Virgin materials supply and primary energy sources use	- Wood supply based on Birch, Douglas, Maritime Pine and Scotch pine roundwood - Energy mainly comes from natural gas (64%) and electricity (36%)	-10.2
Case 2	Recycled materials supply and primary energy sources use	- Wood supply based on recycled materials (mainly crushed pallets) - Energy mainly comes from natural gas (64%) and electricity (36%)	-10.7
Case 3	Recycled materials supply, recovered material used as fuel and primary energy sources use	- Wood supply based on recycled materials (mainly crushed pallets) - Energy recovery from wood products (62%) - Energy mainly comes from natural gas (33%) and electricity (5%)	-12
Case 4	Virgin materials supply, recovered material used as fuel and primary energy sources use	- Wood supply based on Birch, Douglas, Maritime Pine and Scotch pine roundwood - Energy recovery from wood (69%) and bark (31%) - Energy mainly comes from natural gas (33%) and electricity (5%)	-11.7

For module A, the impacts on climate change are negative in all cases thanks to carbon sequestration during the tree's life. In addition, in case of recycling, it is also considered that the carbon content of the previous product is transferred to the recycled material, such as crushed pallets in the example. This allows considering the carbon neutrality of recycled materials, in addition to virgin materials. Unsurprisingly, the most interesting case is the one using recycled materials and recovered materials as fuel (case 3).

Energy recovery is more beneficial in reducing GHG emissions and impact on climate change than using recycled supply materials. Table 18 presents the different cases studied and the results for module C on the climate change indicator.

Table 18 *Parameters and results of module C*

Cases	Situation	Parameters	$e_{\text{module C}}$ (kg CO2e/m ²)
Case 1	Wastes recovered for material use	End of life scenario based on 100% recycling	15.4
Case 2	Wastes recovered for energy production	End of life scenario based on 100% energy recovery	15.4
Case 3	Incineration (energy recovery efficiency lower than 60%)	End of life scenario based on 100% incineration	17.5
Case 4	Landfilling	End of life scenario based on 100% landfilling	8.23

For module C, the material and energy recovery scenarios have the same impact on climate change since module D, which takes into account the environmental costs and benefits associated with the recovery route, is not taken into account yet.

The emissions recorded in these cases 1 and 2 mainly come from:

- The fact that the carbon content of the wood material is transferred to the recycled material. Thus, we consider an emission equivalent to the carbon content of the product in module C.
- Operations on wood products before their recovery (grinding for example).

Case 3 based on the incineration of wood products corresponds to the worst-case scenario for the climate change indicator. Indeed, in this case, and with the assumption of an energy recovery efficiency less than 60%, additional emissions due to the elimination step are considered.

The case of landfill (case 4) is the most interesting concerning the impacts on climate change. This is because, in this end-of-life scenario, part of the carbon content is not re-emitted into the atmosphere in the form of carbon dioxide or methane but remains sequestered in the wood waste.

Finally, Table 19 presents the different end-of-life scenarios studied and the results with module D on the climate change indicator.

Table 19 *Parameters and results of module D*

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Situation</i>	<i>Parameters</i>	<i>e_{module D}</i> <i>(kg CO2e/m²)</i>
Case 1	Wastes recovered for material use	End of life scenario based on 100% recycling	- 4
Case 2	Wastes recovered for energy production	End of life scenario based on 100% energy recovery	- 10,56
Case 3	Incineration (energy recovery efficiency lower than 60%)	End of life scenario based on 100% incineration	- 3,5
Case 4	Landfilling	End of life scenario based on 100% landfilling	0

By considering module D, the impacts on climate change of the first three cases are reduced since the avoided emissions associated with the non-use of virgin materials or primary energy sources are considered.

In the example, the most interesting end-of-life scenario is the one with energy recovery from wood materials since, on the climate change indicator, energy production has much more impact than the production of panels.

Landfilling does not induce any additional load or benefit to the system. It seems to be an interesting recovery route, but it is totally due to the hypothesis where a part of the carbon remains indefinitely in wood waste.

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this report is to provide an overview about the methods assessing environmental impacts of the building materials and give a guidance for implementing LCA methods for the assessment in product development, building components and buildings.

Different method exists to claim environmental friendliness of products. Method could be self-claim or verified method. With the use of Life Cycle Assessment method, impacts from the product behaviour from raw material acquisition until to the product end of life could be quantified.

Benefits from the product utilization after the end of life, through reuse, recycle and energy utilization is claimed separately:

- in LCA method (EN 15804) (see Chapter 3.5), benefits and loads are claimed in a module, which is beyond the life cycle stage (Module D),
- benefits could be claimed also as a 'product handprint' (see Chapter 2.3.2),
- circularity could be claimed by using 'Material flow analysis' (see Chapter 2.4).

If manufacturers want to claim that, their product has beneficial environmental performance - provide full life cycle based LCA.

- Full life cycle assessment gives manufacturers understanding of where their main environmental impacts come from. Are they coming from their manufacturing process or supply chain, from use stage or relatively proportionally through the whole life cycle. Once the source of a high impact has been identified, it allows for a focus on detailed actions to reduce these impacts. This assessment is beneficial during the product development phase (Ecodesign).
- Full life cycle assessment could be communicated as environmental product declaration. EPD provides a structure to ensure that all Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) of construction products, construction services and construction processes are derived, verified, and presented in a harmonised way.
- Calculation guidelines for the life cycle modules A, C and D are given in Chapter 4. Those are given in accordance to the use of 'virgin' material sources and 'recovered' materials. Quantified GWP calculation examples are given for the different raw-material sources used in chipboard case.

If manufacturer wants to claim recyclability – there is no standardized procedure for calculation methodology or which indicators are used for communication. Nevertheless, it is important for companies' own environmental management and for lowering their virgin material and energy consumption to improve their production regarding it is recommended to perform a circularity assessment together with a Life Cycle Assessment. This enables to consider different parameters besides only material cycles.

Even so, that perfect, consistent and precise method for assessment does not exist, different methods are available and described in Chapter 2.4. Manufacturers who want to improve their products must keep circularity assessments very detailed for their products and manufacturing processes.

If designer/constructor/building owner want to study environmental performance of the building - provide full LCA assessment.

In BASAJAUN, one of the overall objectives is to follow raw materials from the forest to the rural areas until their final application in urban buildings. This tie together of information from virgin materials until products involves several steps of transformations and hence several chances or risks for environmental and resource benefits or burdens. It should be highlighted that environmental performance and resource efficiency are being developed and calculated on various levels not only throughout a singles product lifecycle, because the final building compiles many products into an aggregated one. For the implementation of the general assessment, advanced methodologies presented above give a generic red line for specific products, but the different levels of detail and data must be considered carefully. Each level has various stakeholders involved with different objectives and different contributions.

Figure 19 Chevron-List diagram for the development of environmental information.

For a complete overview on the environmental and circularity assessment, the Chevron-List above describes the involvement of stakeholders and the modules for which the data must be acquired. The Chevron diagram above shows in vertical order the steps in the development of environmental information. It names responsibility for each step within the BASAJAUN project. The steps start with the material development and after construction of demos, end with an ex-post (as-built) assessment of environmental and circularity performance. Along the horizontal axis the modules of environmental loads or burdens of product(-s) are described for which information and data must be collected and processed by the responsible entities. The horizontal processes are iterative and are done several times to i.e. improve a specific product until its optimal performance. Finally, all modules within one layer are aggregated respect each of the final product(-s) and handed over to the next level below.

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Basajaun is a European innovation action about sustainable building with wood. The main objective is to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimized to foster both rural development and urban transformation whilst being connected with sustainable forest management in Europe. The consortium comprises 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 15 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The project is coordinated by the Tecnalia Research and Innovation Foundation in Spain

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